

Second-Generation Ethanol production from Steam Exploded Barley Straw by *Kluyveromyces marxianus* CECT 10875

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Abstract

Barley straw is nowadays being considered a potential lignocellulosic raw material for fuel-ethanol production as an alternative to starch- or sugar-containing feedstock. In this work, several configuration strategies for ethanol production from steam-exploded barley straw by *Kluyveromyces marxianus* CECT 10875 have been studied with the aim of obtaining higher ethanol concentrations.

Different substrate loading (2-15%, w/v) were studied during enzymatic hydrolysis. The xylanase contribution on glucose production and glucan conversion at different substrate loading was also investigated. In addition, three different process configurations, separate hydrolysis and fermentation, simultaneous saccharification and fermentation and presaccharification and simultaneous saccharification, were compared at different water insoluble solids concentration (5, 10 and 15%). The influence of xylanase addition on the ethanol yield was studied as well.

Results show that endo-xylanases improved glucan conversion and ethanol yield compared with a standard enzymatic mixture, markedly at low substrate concentration. The positive effect of added xylanase was most evident at early stages of enzymatic hydrolysis. Regarding process configurations for the period of 72 hours, SSF with endo-xylanases provided the best ethanol yield, nearly 70%, for 10% WIS. Nonetheless, the higher ethanol concentration, 29.4 g/l, was obtained at 15% WIS.

Keywords: ethanol, barley straw, steam explosion pretreatment, SSF, thermotolerant yeast.

1. Introduction

Ethanol production from biomass has gained considerable interest in order to provide energy security and reduce greenhouse-gas emissions. Lignocellulosic biomass offers many potential advantages in comparison with the traditionally used sugar or starch biomass for its large quantity and not competing with food and feed production. Furthermore, lignocellulosic ethanol has shown to involve up to 85% net reduction in greenhouse-gas emissions [1]. The abundance and high carbohydrate content of barley straw make it a good candidate for bioethanol production in Europe [2].

Typical ethanol production from lignocellulose biomass consists of four steps: pretreatment, enzymatic hydrolysis, fermentation and product purification. The success of this kind of processes depends largely on the global yield of ethanol production (volume of ethanol produced per dry weight of raw material) and high ethanol concentration in the fermentation media. Ethanol concentrations superior to 4% (v/v) contribute to diminish the energy demand in the distillation stage, making ethanol production from lignocellulosic material economically profitable [3]. The amount of ethanol originated in the fermentation step mainly depends on the sugars production during enzymatic hydrolysis. Higher substrate concentrations lead to higher hydrolyzed sugars concentration; which are preferable for the fermentation step. A high solids loading will also contribute to the reduction of global production costs as a consequence of lower water consumption and lower downstream processing cost [1]. Nevertheless, increasing the solids loading presents some difficulties that restrict the maximum loading of solids such as end product inhibition of enzymes by glucose and cellobiose, mass transfer limitations and, if the whole slurry is used, larger amount of inhibitors originated during pretreatment. Strategies to increase the solids loading in enzymatic hydrolysis and fermentation include the application of fed-batch processes [4-5], constant removal of glucose [6] and development of bioreactors with improved mixing capacity and low energy consumption [7-8].

Enzymatic hydrolysis and fermentation of the hydrolyzed biomass can be carried out in different process configurations such as separate hydrolysis and fermentation (SHF) and simultaneous saccharification and fermentation (SSF). SSF configuration process is a promising option since it is carried out in one vessel and end-product inhibition is minimized, allowing higher solids levels [9]. The main disadvantage of SSF compared to SHF is that it is usually conducted at temperatures inferior to the optimum of the cellulolytic enzymes. The application of a presaccharification step prior to SSF has been proposed to reduce the viscosity of the slurry at high substrate loading [10]. Ethanol yield could be also improved in a SSF process by using thermotolerant yeast such as *Kluyveromyces marxianus*, which can ferment ethanol at temperatures close to the optimum of enzymatic hydrolysis (between 38 and 45 °C)

[11]. *K. marxianus* is gaining considerable attention due to its desirable properties including a broad spectrum of sugars utilization, high secretory capacity and extremely rapid growth rate [12]. Furthermore, the application of higher temperatures during SSF can lead to several-fold reduction cost for large-scale commercial fuel ethanol including reduction of cooling cost and risk of contamination, and better performance of saccharolytic enzymes with subsequent reduction on enzyme dosage in comparison with SHF [11]. The efficiency of *Kluyveromyces marxianus* CECT 10875 on SSF of various lignocellulosic biomasses have been previously evaluated and results showed ethanol yields in the range of 50-72% of the theoretical in 72-82 h depending on material tested [4,13].

The high cost of enzymes calls for lower enzyme dosages while still achieving high sugars yields [1]. The reduction of protein requirements could be achieved by reconstituting the enzyme mixture to include other activities than just cellulase and β -glucosidase [14]. In this context, a moderate enzyme dosage (7 FPU/g substrate, corresponding to a protein concentration of 14.4 mg/g substrate) constituted by cellulase and β -glucosidase was applied in steam-exploded barley straw and its performance was compared with an enzyme mixture of similar protein content which included also xylanase in a dosage selected from a previous study on enzymatic hydrolysis at 5% solids loading [15]. The effect of xylanase supplementation, substrate loading (2-15% solids loading) and incubation time (12-120 hours) was firstly evaluated in enzymatic hydrolysis carried out under its optimum conditions. In addition, the effect of these parameters on ethanol production in different process configurations namely separate hydrolysis and fermentation (SHF), presaccharification and simultaneous saccharification (PSSF) and simultaneous saccharification and fermentation (SSF) using the thermotolerant yeast *Kluyveromyces marxianus* CECT 10875 [16] was also evaluated.

2. Material and Methods.

2.1. Raw Material

Barley straw (*Hordeum vulgare*, 6-7% moisture), supplied by Ecocarburantes de Castilla y León (Spain) was used as raw material. Raw material showed the following composition (% dry weight): 37.1 \pm 1.3 glucans, 21.3 \pm 0.5 xylans, 3.8 \pm 0.4; arabinans, 1.2 \pm 0.2 galactans, 16.9 \pm 0.7 acid insoluble lignin, 2.3 \pm 0.8 acid soluble lignin; 1.8 \pm 0.01 acetyl groups; 15.4 \pm 0.4 extractives and 8.2 \pm 0.3 ash. The composition of the raw material was determined using the standard Laboratory Analytical Procedures for biomass analysis provided by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) (Colorado, USA) [17].

2.2. Pretreatment

The barley straw was pretreated in a steam explosion prototype small plant using Masonite technology which consists of 2L reactor designed to reach a maximum operating pressure of 4.12 MPa and it is equipped with a quick-opening ball valve, an electronic device programmed for accurate control of steam time and temperature described in a previous work [13]. After pretreatment the material was recovered in a cyclone, and the slurry was cooled about 40 °C and filtered for solid and liquid fraction recovery. The liquid fraction was analysed for sugar and byproducts concentration. The solid fraction was thoroughly washed with water and dried at 45 °C. Pretreatment conditions (210 °C for 5 min) were previously selected at the most adequate in terms of hemicellulose-derived sugar recovery in the liquid fraction, and enzymatic hydrolysis yield [18].

2.3. Enzymes

Celluclast 1.5L FG, Novozym 188 and NS50013, NS50010 and NS50030 enzyme preparations were kindly provided by Novozymes. The three last preparations were contained in Novozymes Biomass Kit for conversion of lignocellulosic materials.

Cellulase and β -glucosidase activities were measured according to methods described by Ghose [19]. Cellulase activity was defined in terms of filter paper units (FPU/ml) and β -glucosidase as cellobiase units (IU/ml). Xylanase activity was quantified as described Bailey et al. [20] using birchwood xylan (Sigma, USA) as substrate. One unit of xylanase activity is the amount of enzyme required to release 1 μ mol of reducing sugars (xylose equivalents) per min (U/ml). The protein content of the enzymes preparations was determined by BCATM assay (BCA-Compat-Able Protein Assay kit, ref 23229, Pierce, Rockford IL) using bovine serum albumin as protein standard. The main enzymatic activities and protein concentration of the enzyme preparations are summarized in Table 1.

2.4. Substrate

The solid fraction obtained after filtration of the pretreated barley straw was thoroughly washed and it was used as substrate for the different assays. The composition of this fraction, denoted as water insoluble solid (WIS), was determined with the standard Laboratory Analytical Procedures for biomass analysis provided by NREL except for the extractives determination [17] and was expressed as percentage based on oven-dried material.

2.5. Enzymatic Hydrolysis Test

Two different enzymes mixtures were employed in every assay: a standard enzyme mixture, which consisted of Celluclast 1.5L FG and Novozyme 188, and a mixture which included NS50013 (cellulase), NS50010 (β -glucosidase) and NS50030 (endo-xylanase). Enzyme dosage of the different

enzyme preparations is expressed as volume of enzyme preparation (E)/100 g substrate (S). Cellulases and xylanases were dosed at 10 and 5% (v/w) E/S respectively, while β -glucosidase was dosed always at 1% (v/w) E/S. These enzyme dosage corresponded with an enzyme activity of 7 FPU, 8.4 IU β -glucosidase and 72 U xylanase per gram of WIS and a protein concentration of 14.4 mg/g WIS for the standard enzyme mixture and an enzyme activity of 6.6 FPU, 11.4 IU β -glucosidase and 320 U xylanase per gram of WIS and a protein concentration of 17 mg/g WIS for the mixture which included xylanase.

Enzymatic hydrolysis experiments were performed in 250 ml Erlenmeyer flasks in 100 ml of 0.05 M citrate buffer (pH 4.8) at 2, 5, 10 and 15% w/v substrate loading at 50 °C and 150 rpm. Samples were withdrawn from the hydrolysis media at 1, 3, 6, 12, 24, 72 and 120 hours and boiled for 5 minutes to stop the reaction. The initial samples were ten-times diluted to reduce overestimation of the degree of glucan conversion at high substrate loading [21]. The samples were centrifuged at 12,000 g for 10 min, and sugar concentration (glucose, cellobiose and xylose) was determined by HPLC as it is described elsewhere [22]. Additionally, blanks of the enzyme mixtures prepared for each substrate loading were analyzed by HPLC to subtract the sugar content present in the enzyme preparations used [23]. All experiments were performed at least in duplicate and average results are shown.

2.6. Microorganism

Kluyveromyces marxianus CECT 10875, a thermotolerant yeast strain, was used in fermentation on SSF, PSSF and SHF experiments. Active cultures for inoculation were prepared by growing the yeast on a rotary shaker at 150 rpm for 16 h at 42 °C in a growth medium (initial pH 5.5) containing: 5 g/l of yeast extract (Difco), 2 g/l of NH_4Cl , 1 g/l of KH_2PO_4 , 0.3 g/l of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 30 g/l of glucose.

2.7. Process configurations

2.7.1. Simultaneous Saccharification and Fermentation

The SSF experiments were carried out in 250 ml Erlenmeyer flask, each containing 60 ml of fermentation medium (growth medium described above), which were agitated at 150 rpm. Glucose was substituted by dry pretreated substrate concentration. Enzymes were also added as in enzymatic hydrolysis tests. In the SSF experiments, flask were inoculated with a low inoculum size [4% (v/v) yeast cultures (corresponding to a cell addition as dry weight of 0.2 g/l)], and experiments were conducted at 42 °C for 72 h. Substrate concentration were 5, 10 and 15% (w/v). Samples were withdrawn after 1, 3, 6, 9, 12, 24, 48 and 72 hours, and were analysed for ethanol and sugars.

2.7.2. Separate Hydrolysis and Fermentation

The enzymatic hydrolysis tests were run for 48 hours at 50 °C. The hydrolysis media was filtered and the liquid fraction was submitted to fermentation stage at 42 °C by adding 0.2 g/l of cells and salts described above.

2.7.3. Presaccharification and Simultaneous Saccharification and Fermentation

The presaccharification and subsequent run were also performed in 250 ml Erlenmeyer flask. The presaccharification stage was run for 24 h at 50 °C, after which the temperature was reduced to 42 °C and nutrients and yeast were added, which turned the process into a SSF. The experiments were run for another 48 hours. Samples were withdrawn at 24 h during presaccharification and after 0, 3, 9, 24 and 48 h of PSSF, and analysed for ethanol and sugars.

2.8. Analytical Method

The concentrations of sugars (glucose, cellobiose and xylose) and byproducts (carboxylic acids, furans and phenolic compounds) were determined by HPLC as described elsewhere [22]. Ethanol was measured by gas chromatography, using a HP 5890 Series II apparatus equipped with an Agilent 6890 series injector, a flame ionization detector and a column of Carbowax 20 M at 85 °C. The injector and detector temperature was maintained at 150 °C.

All analytical determinations were performed in duplicate and average results are shown.

2.9. Calculations

The glucan conversion (GC) was calculated as the hydrolysed glucan divided by the glucan content in the WIS and expressed as percentage. The hydrolysed glucan (HC) was calculated considering the glucose and cellobiose content in the media, after applying weight adjustment for analyzed sugars. GC was calculated as follows:

$$GC (\%) = ([\text{glucose}] + 1.053 [\text{cellobiose}]) / 1.111 f [\text{biomass}] \times 100$$

where, [Glucose] and [Cellobiose] are the concentrations (g/l) of glucose and cellobiose in the supernatant, respectively; [Biomass] is the dry biomass concentration at the beginning of the hydrolysis (g/L); f is the glucan fraction in dry biomass (g/g); 1.053 and 1.111 are factors to determine equivalents of glucose from cellobiose and glucan respectively.

The volumetric ethanol productivity at 24 hours was calculated based on ethanol concentration at 24 hours divided by the number of hours.

Ethanol yield for the three configurations is reported in terms of ethanol produced from glucose consumed (Y_{ETOH}) and as percentage of the theoretical (0.51 g ethanol/g glucose), assuming that all the potential glucose in the WIS fraction was available for fermentation.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Pretreated material composition

Pretreatment conditions which results in both high sugars recovery and cellulose fibres with enhanced digestibility to enzymatic attack were chosen from a previous study [18]. The composition of the steam-pretreated barley straw is shown in Table 2. The solubilisation of hemicellulose and extractives during the steam explosion pretreatment led to an enrichment of glucan and acid insoluble lignin in the solid fraction, which constituted 58.6 and 21.6% on dry weight basis, respectively. The residual hemicellulose was constituted by xylan (6.2% w/w dry weight). These results are in agreement with values reported in literature for steam-explosion pretreatment of barley straw [24]. Based on this composition, a substrate loading above 15% would be needed to reach an ethanol concentration of 4% (w/v) considering a cellulose conversion yield of 80% and a fermentation yield of 0.45 g ethanol/g glucose.

The composition of the liquid fraction is also summarized in Table 2. The prehydrolysate of steam exploded barley straw consisted of a mixture of sugars (25.2 g/l) and degradation products including carboxylic acids (2.95 g/l), phenols (0.23 g/l), and furans (0.89 g/l). Sugars were presented in a considerable proportion as oligomers. Regarding carbohydrates the major sugar released was the xylose being in a concentration of 17 g/l.

3.2. Effect of the substrate loading and xylanase addition on enzymatic hydrolysis

The solid fraction from steam pretreated barley straw was thoroughly washed to remove sugars solubilised during pretreatment and potential inhibitors (Table 2) that could affect both enzymatic hydrolysis [22] and fermentation [25]. The effect of xylanase addition, solid loading and incubation time on glucose release and glucan conversion was evaluated.

In order to assess differences in enzymes mixtures efficiency, samples were taken during the first 12 hours where end-product inhibition is minimized. Figure 1 shows the kinetic of glucose (1A) and xylose (1B) production (g/l) for the different substrate concentrations in the first 12 hours with both enzymes mixtures. Increasing substrate loading led to a higher glucose and xylose concentrations for both enzyme formulations. The highest glucose and xylose concentrations were obtained using 15% substrate loading (44.2 g/l of glucose and 1.8 g/l of xylose) with xylanase supplementation. Glucan conversion at 12 hours was also evaluated according to the glucan content in the WIS (Table 2). These values are represented in Table 3. Glucan conversion decreased a 7.3 and 14.1% when increasing solids level from 2 to 15% for the standard mixture and the enzyme mixture which included xylanase, respectively.

The enzymatic hydrolysis was kept up to 120 hours to verify whether longer incubation times could enhance the glucan conversion at higher solids loading for the same enzyme: substrate loading (Table

3). Glucan conversions about 59% were obtained at 15% WIS loading for the standard and the xylanase mixtures, 19 and 11 % more than those obtained at 12 hours. In contrast, almost a complete glucan conversion (98.7%) was obtained at 2% WIS (w/v) when using xylanase. Although the supplementation with xylanase provided higher glucan conversions values than the standard enzyme mixture, these differences were more evident at early stages of the hydrolysis and at lower substrate loading (Table 3).

The addition of xylanase to the enzymatic hydrolysis media is becoming a common practise in order to reduce the enzyme dosage in pretreated materials with residual xylan [26-30]. Similar glucan conversion to that presented here was obtained for steam-exploded corn stover when xylanases were added to the media at 2% WIS (w/v) [28]. Increments of 5 % in glucan conversion at 72 hours have been reported for steam-exploded corn stover with similar xylan content to the substrate used in this work (6% dw) when the media was supplemented with xylanase (60 mg/g glucan) at a solids loading of 8% (w/v) [26]. In our study, the addition of lower dosage of xylanase (3.8 mg/g glucan) increased glucan conversion in 15% when the solid loading was 10% for the same incubation period (Table 3).

The results presented herein indicate that the addition of xylanase in the enzyme mixture enhances glucan hydrolysis of steam-pretreated barley straw markedly at low substrate loading and at early stages of enzymatic hydrolysis. It has been suggested that xylanases improve glucan hydrolysis by removing non-cellulosic polysaccharides and thus, enhancing accessibility of the cellulases to more cellulose chains [14]. However, the low values of xylan conversion obtained during enzymatic hydrolysis (less than 30%); suggest another mechanism rather than the removal of xylan coating cellulose chains to explain the improvement in glucan conversion by xylanases. Consistent with this finding, a previous study demonstrated that the improvement on glucan conversion by xylanase addition was observed in steam-pretreated barley straw with low residual xylan (less than 3% dw) [15]. Additionally, parallel experiments performed on commercial cellulose, Sigmacell, showed an increment of 15 and 11% in glucan conversion at 12 hours when xylanases were added to the hydrolysis media at 5 and 10% of substrate loading respectively (data not shown). The glucan conversion could also be affected by sugars and oligomers released during hydrolysis. As reported recently by Qing *et al.* [31], the low xylanase activity in cellulases commercial enzymes produces a significant amount of xylooligomers during enzymatic hydrolysis of biomass solids that contain xylan, and these xylooligomers are strongly inhibitory to cellulases [31]. Removing xylooligomers by β -xylosidase (activity present also in xylanase preparation used in this work) could reduce inhibition and speed conversion.

The higher hydrolytic efficiency of the mixture which included xylanases was reduced when increasing the solids concentration at longer incubation periods. The reduction of glucan conversion with the increasing

solid concentration is in line with other studies performed on steam-exploded lignocellulose [32-33]. There are numerous factors that could contribute to the reduction in the capacity of cellulose conversion by enzymes, including end-product inhibition, un-productive binding to lignin or cellulose and changes in substrate reactivity during enzymatic hydrolysis [34]. Besides, long exposure to temperature and mixing could contribute to enzyme deactivation [35]. Among all these factors, end-product inhibition has been suggested as the most influential [36]. In the case of the synergism induced by addition of xylanase, it has been demonstrated that the crystallinity of biomass has an important impact [27].

Since glucose concentration is directly related to the solids concentration in the media, the application of the maximum solids loading possible whilst keeping a reasonable glucan conversion is recommended. Figure 2 plots the glucose concentration and glucan conversion as a function of the solids loading for both enzymes mixtures at 72 hours. Substrate loading of above 12% (w/v) would provide a compromise between hydrolysis efficiency and glucose concentration for the same enzyme: substrate ratio for both enzymes mixtures. This solid loading would result in a glucose concentration of approximately 52 g/l and a glucan conversion of 72% when the enzyme mixture included xylanase.

3.3. Simultaneous saccharification and fermentation with by the thermotolerant yeast *Kluyveromyces marxianus*

The performance of thermotolerant yeast *Kluyveromyces marxianus* was evaluated during SSF of steam-exploded barley straw for an incubation period of 72 hours using a moderate enzyme dosage (7 FPU/g WIS). All the experiments were performed using the washed solid fraction as substrate since this yeast has been shown to be inhibited by compounds originated during steam-explosion [4]. In an attempt to obtain an ethanol concentration close to 4% (v/v), the experiments were carried out with a substrate loading of 15% (w/v). Additionally, experiments with 5 and 10% WIS (w/v) were performed in order to study the effect of substrate loading on ethanol production by *K. marxianus*. The influence of xylanase addition on the ethanol yield was also evaluated.

Figure 3 represents the time course for SSF process with 5, 10 and 15% (w/v) of WIS substrate loading with both enzyme mixtures. Glucose accumulation in fermentation media was only observed during the first six hours, showing good yeast fermentation performance with low inoculum content (0.2 g/l). Glucose concentrations were lower than 2 g/l at 5% (w/v) during the first hour, while at 10% (w/v) these amounts did not exceed 4 g/l. The lag phase was extended up to 10 hours when the substrate loading was 15% (w/v). This delay or lag phase is due to the adaptation of the yeast to fermentation conditions and its duration is related with the solids loading [37]. A longer lag phase in SSF performed at

high solids loading of other lignocellulosic materials has been reported using a higher inoculum volume of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* [24, 38].

After 24 hours after inoculation, ethanol production rate was reduced markedly for the SSF performed at lower substrate loading. Ethanol volumetric productivity values at 24 hours were 0.30, 0.68 and 0.66 g/l·h for 5, 10 and 15% WIS (w/v) respectively (Table 4). The addition of xylanase resulted in higher ethanol volumetric productivities at 24 hours: 0.40, 0.75 and 0.77 g/l·h for 5, 10 and 15% WIS (w/v) respectively. Likewise, the maximum ethanol concentration, 29.4 g/l, was obtained at 15% WIS loading (w/v) when including xylanases, resulting in 12% more ethanol than the originated with just cellulase and beta-glucosidase. This ethanol concentration corresponds to an ethanol yield of 59.4% of the theoretical based on the glucose content of the WIS. However, the maximum ethanol yield, 67.4%, was reached for 10% WIS when xylanases were added to the SSF. This yield corresponds well with those obtained in SSF of pretreated switchgrass at lower solids loading (8% of WIS) and 10 FPU/g WIS using several strains of *Kluyveromyces marxianus* at 72 hours [39].

3.4. Comparison of SSF with SHF and PSSF processes

SSF was compared with other process configurations for a final period of 72 hours. The enzymatic hydrolysis was kept 48 hours and 24 h hours in the SHF and PSSF respectively before inoculation. Results of ethanol yield, volumetric ethanol productivity at 24 hours of fermentation, and ethanol concentration for both enzymes mixtures at 72 hours are listed in Table 4. SSF configuration provided the highest ethanol concentrations and ethanol yields at 72 hours for substrate concentrations higher than 5% WIS (w/v). Compared to SSF, the ethanol volumetric productivity at 24 hours increased from 0.66-0.77 g·l⁻¹·h⁻¹ to 0.79-0.96 and 0.99-1.1 g·l⁻¹·h⁻¹ when applying respectively SHF and PSSF at 15% WIS loading (w/v).

As indicated by the results, the addition of xylanase increased the ethanol yield for all configurations evaluated. The enhancement of fermentation performance by adding xylanase has been established in earlier works [10, 40] providing support to the fact that it is possible to reduce the enzyme concentration needed by incorporating other enzyme activities than cellulase and β-glucosidase also during fermentation.

Among the configurations herein studied, SSF configuration provided the best ethanol yield compared with SHF and PSSF for solids loading higher than 5%. The better performance of SSF versus SHF has been previously reported in the literature for other steam-exploded materials [39-41]. The best effectiveness of SSF compared to SHF and PSSF may be due to prevention of both end-product inhibition and thermal deactivation of the enzymes [24].

4. Conclusions

An overall economic process must include reaching a high ethanol yield at high substrate loading and reduced enzyme loading over short residence times. For the material used in this study, steam-exploded barley straw, substrate loading about 15% is needed to reach an ethanol concentration of 4% (w/v) which is considered as a benchmark for reducing distillation costs. In this work, the highest glucose concentration (56.4 g/l) was obtained at 15% substrate loading during EH under optimum conditions with xylanase addition. However, a concentration of 12% of WIS (w/v) would provide a compromise between hydrolysis efficiency and glucose levels for the same enzyme: substrate ratio at 72 hours. Xylanase supplementation during EH enhanced the hydrolysis effectiveness, mainly at low substrate loading at initial phase of hydrolysis. This positive effect has been observed on ethanol yield obtained for the three configuration processes studied: SHF, SSF and PSSF.

Among the three configurations compared, PSSF and SSF configurations allowed larger substrate concentration than SHF for the studied range (5-15% of WIS). Ethanol concentration close to 3% (w/v) was obtained by SSF at 15% WIS loading. However, the highest ethanol yield after 72 hours, 67.4% which corresponds to an ethanol concentration of 22 g/l, was achieved with SSF at 10% WIS with the xylanase mixture. It was thus concluded that SSF was better process configuration compared to SHF and PSSF since it alleviates end-product inhibition and avoids enzyme deactivation. Besides, the thermotolerant yeast *Kluyveromyces marxianus* CECT 10875 was shown to adapt rapidly to the media at low inoculum volume [4% (v/v)].

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Figure captions

Figure 1. (A) Glucose and (B) xylose released (g/l) during initial phase of enzymatic hydrolysis of steam-exploded barley straw at different WIS concentrations (% w/v) with a standard enzyme mixture (closed symbols) or a mixture which included xylanase (opened symbols): (◆, ◇) 2%, (▲, Δ) 5%, (■, □,) 10% and (●, ○) 15 %.

Figure 2. Glucose released (g/l) and glucan conversion (%) at 72 hours of enzymatic hydrolysis of steam-exploded barley straw.

(-◆-) (--◇--) glucose and (-●-) (--○--) glucan conversion for the standard enzyme mixture (closed symbols) and the mixture which included xylanase (opened symbols).

Figure 3. Time course for ethanol (◆, ◇), glucose (●, ○), cellobiose (■, □) and xylose (▲, Δ) during SSF using the standard enzyme mixture (closed symbols) or the mixture which included xylanase (opened symbols) at different substrate loading (A) 5%, (B) 10% and (C) 15 %.

Table 1

Table 1. Enzymes activities and protein concentration of the enzymes preparations

Enzyme preparation	Protein concentration (mg/ml)	Cellulase activity (FPU/ml)	β -glucosidase activity (IU/ml)	Xylanase activity (U/ml)
Celluclast 1.5 L FG	151.3 \pm 8.0	65.16 \pm 2.7	11.7 \pm 0.3	660.0 \pm 49.3
NS50013	137.6 \pm 15.1	62.5 \pm 2.8	8.0 \pm 0.2	1117.3 \pm 97.4
Novozyme 188	82.8 \pm 6.0	0.23 \pm 0.04	664.3 \pm 4.5	68.9 \pm 5.3
NS50010	141.3 \pm 12.2	0.29 \pm 0.06	992.0 \pm 9.6	124.4 \pm 9.5
NS50030	20.8 \pm 4.3	0.30 \pm 0.01	1.0 \pm 0.01	3760.0 \pm 294.6

Table 2. Composition of steam-pretreated barley straw expressed as % dry weight in the WIS fraction and as g/l in the liquid fraction.

Water Insoluble Solids (% dry weight)		Liquid Fraction (g/l)	
Glucan	58.6±1.5	Glucose	4.6±0.6
		Xylose	17.4±1.5
Xylan	6.2±0.8	Arabinose	1.9±0.3
		Galactose	1.3±0.4
Acid Insoluble Lignin	21.6±1.4	Carboxylic acids	2.95±0.8
		Phenols	0.23±0.08
Ashes	9.1±1.4	Furans	0.89±0.2

Table 3

Table 3. Glucan conversion (%) of washed-WIS at varying hydrolysis time and solids loading.

Hydrolysis time (h)	Glucan conversion (%)							
	Standard enzyme mixture				Xylanase mixture			
	Water Insoluble Solids concentration (%)							
	2	5	10	15	2	5	10	15
12	47.3 ± 2.1	45.8 ± 3.0	40.4 ± 2.4	39.9 ± 4.2	62.5 ± 3.1	54.9 ± 0.9	47.9 ± 0.7	48.4 ± 3.8
24	58.1 ± 0.7	57.2 ± 3.2	49.4 ± 3.5	52.2 ± 1.8	71.4 ± 2.2	70.2 ± 2.1	58.4 ± 2.7	55.8 ± 2.6
48	63.8 ± 1.3	62.6 ± 0.4	57.7 ± 1.1	57.2 ± 0.9	76.7 ± 1.7	73.1 ± 2.7	64.6 ± 0.8	58.7 ± 1.5
72	70.3 ± 1.8	69.0 ± 0.3	63.0 ± 0.9	57.5 ± 2.3	78.1 ± 0.4	79.3 ± 2.8	74.7 ± 3.4	58.9 ± 3.1
120	86.7 ± 0.9	80.2 ± 2.5	72.1 ± 4.1	58.7 ± 3.1	98.7 ± 1.6	92.1 ± 0.7	77.7 ± 0.2	59.2 ± 2.3

Table 4

Table 4. Ethanol fermentation yield ($Y_{E/G}$) expressed as g ethanol/g glucose consumed, volumetric ethanol productivity (Q_E) expressed as $g \cdot l^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$ at 24 hours and ethanol concentration reached at 72 hours of the different process configurations with the standard enzyme mixture and the mixture which included also xylanases for different substrate loading.

Process configuration	%WIS loading (w/v)	Standard mixture			Xylanase mixture		
		$Y_{E/G}$	Q_E ($g \cdot l^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$) 24 h fermentation	Ethanol (g/l) at 72 h of the process	$Y_{E/G}$	Q_E ($g \cdot l^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$) 24 h fermentation	Ethanol (g/l) at 72 h of the process
SSF	5	0.23	0.30	7.4 ± 0.3	0.30	0.40	9.6 ± 0.3
	10	0.30	0.68	19.4 ± 0.3	0.34	0.75	22.2 ± 0.3
	15	0.27	0.66	26.0 ± 0.3	0.30	0.77	29.4 ± 0.3
SHF	5	0.23	0.31	7.4 ± 0.3	0.29	0.38	9.1 ± 0.2
	10	0.23	0.63	14.7 ± 0.9	0.26	0.68	16.4 ± 0.2
	15	0.19	0.79	18.9 ± 1.1	0.24	0.96	23.0 ± 0.4
PSSF	5	0.24	0.32	7.8 ± 0.4	0.29	0.37	9.5 ± 0.3
	10	0.25	0.68	16.1 ± 0.2	0.28	0.73	18.1 ± 0.4
	15	0.25	0.99	24.1 ± 0.2	0.27	1.1	26.3 ± 0.4

Figure 1A and 1B

Figure 1A

Figure 1B

Figure 2

Figure 2

Figure 3

